

Capitalism and Environmental Damage: The Root Cause and the Impossibility of Current Corrective Measures

Nelson M. Ishengoma

Department of Sociology & Anthropology
University of Dodoma (UDOM), Tanzania
Contact: ishengomanelson@gmail.com

Abstract

Despite the environment being the fundamental source of life to all living things, yet numerous reports claim that the environment is now in a more precarious state than ever before. While the paper acknowledges that various denouement factors such as deforestation, high number of industries, chemical effluents, unprecedented construction, secondary pollutants, population explosion, and unplanned land-use policies have had significant debilitating effects on environment, such factors are inadequate both at the level of understanding and averting the problem. Instead, efforts to diagnose and address the problem need to acknowledge the nature and processes of the current social-relations that act as the substratum upon which exploitative relations and destructive environmental activities are anchored. Under the logic of capitalist production and exchange, and with the search for profits being the goal that overrides all others, adverse effects on the environment are inevitable. It is from the understanding of capitalism as the root cause of the environmental problems that this paper rejects the prevailing illusive and oxymoron solutions that fail to confront capitalism; such solutions, in actual fact, maintain and nurture the problem. In order to address the problem, the paper suggests a systemic transformation where the new forms of social relations that would be geared towards meeting the needs of everyone, including the environment without compromising the value of each, unlike the current capitalism-based social relations that serve a privileged few and encourage environmental damage. This paper is a result of a desk review of various relevant journal articles, reports and other gray literature, with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of the causes of environmental damage and various associated solutions from the perspective of social relations.

Key words: Environmental/ecological problems, Capitalism, Corrective measures

1.0: Introduction

By and large, personal endeavors are inherently created from prevailing social relations, which are translated into individual behavior for sustenance, replication, and justification (Berger and Luckman, 1966; Bean, 2009; Blumer, 1969; Major et al., 2005). While acknowledging the consciousness and power of individuals to react, manipulate and realign predefined models, their choices are all the time constrained and provided within the prevailing system. According to Marx “an individual’s decisions and options do not have their own existence; rather they exist within a certain social formation” (Marx in Morrison: 1983). Indeed, many socio-cultural studies attest that social and cultural problems will not be adequately redressed and addressed until there is a thorough understanding of the morals and ethics of the system upon which such maladies are generated, anchored, reinforced, and celebrated. It is from this sociological angle that the capitalism-environmental damage nexus should be analysed.

An examination of the major underlying causes for environmental problems, a number of remedies, and evolution of many such problems have long adopted the non-organismic strategies. Throughout the previous three decades, the causes have been traced and analysed in light of how each symptomatic element either facilitate or directly contribute in harming the environment (World Resources Institute, 2012; Ecology Global Network, 2011; Hajer, 2005) and not how each is created. As a result, denouement elements such as deforestation, high number of industries, chemical effluents, unprecedented construction, secondary pollutants, population explosion, and unplanned land-use policies, amongst others, have for a long time dominated the “environmental problems” discourse. It is from this theoretical analysis where solutions for the same have long emanated and provide futile (Environmental Protection Agency, 2012; Hajer, 2005; Ehrlich and Holdren, 1991).

In the light of Marx’s (1845) conception of the capitalist society, the thoughts of the presiding class are in every historical era the ruling thoughts. This is demonstrated and reinforced in every aspect of human life including the very fundamental process and means of mental production. It is from its dominance in material possession and

production that the thoughts of many who lack the means of mental production become subject to it. As such, this is to affirm, therefore, that the decisions and options which men carry on exist in particular social systems which are imperative to their existence, but yet independent of their will. They correspond to a definite stage of the level of their material forces of production. The sum total of such relations of production forms the economic base of the society, which is the real foundation upon which the legal and political superstructures which correspond to specific forms of social consciousness are elevated.

...It is not the consciousness of men, therefore, that determines their existence, but instead their social existence determines their consciousness (Marx in Morrison, 1983).

It goes without say, therefore, that the environmental damage cannot be analysed in isolation from the capitalist system. It is from the capital social relations epoch where the ethics and morals that guide subsequent environmental actions can be understood and contended with.

This position should, however, not sound like an attempt to entirely exempt human actions from damaging the environment. Indeed, time immemorial, ecological problems, particularly those associated with deforestation, soil erosion, and salinisation of irrigated soils go back to ancient times and very much so associated with human activities. As Plato admitted in Jowett, Benjamin (1871: 114)

... what evidence then can we provide that it is... just a mere leftover of what it used to be? We are left with nothing but the skeleton of a body like squandered by illness; the rich, fertile soil has been washed away leaving the land skinned. In any case, in those days the harm had not occurred, the slopes had high peaks, the rough plane of Phelleus was secured with rich soil, and the mountains were secured by thick woods, of which there are few tracks today. For a few mountains which today will can merely support honey bees, not so long ago produced roof beams for gigantic structures whose roofs are still standing. There were also a sizeable number of tall and huge cultivated trees which bore boundless amounts of feed for animals and creatures. The earth profited from a yearly rainfall which did not run to wash off the soil as it is the case today, however, was absorbed in larger quantities and retained in spongy layers of soil, so that what was sipped down, streamed downwards into the valleys and appeared in a multitude of springs and rivers. Tabernacles and

temples that yet still lives at these past springs are confirmation of the account....

This piece argues against the motives, ethics and underlying philosophy guiding such human actions. What is so clear between the current and previous social relations is that in the current social capital relations the hunger for needless consumption and exploitation of nature is unprecedented, highly encouraged, and profitable; and the technologies that can do much greater damage and do it more quickly are mounting (World Resources Institute, 2012; Ecology Global Network, 2011). Such attributes are fundamentally the upshot of the capitalistic economic system that knows no bounds and a spring of many other apparent factors.

2.0: Methods

Considering the fact that numerous researches are produced each year, often with conflicting conclusions and findings possibly due to study contexts, timings, and sampling variation amongst others which creates uncertainty on what the overall actually is, or which evidences are most trustworthy and therefore ought to be used as the ground for policy decisions and practice, this particular study deployed a systematic review approach. This approach aimed at addressing these problems by identifying, assessing and integrating the evidences and findings of all the relevant, high-quality individual studies in addressing the problem of environmental damage in the capitalism. In its endeavor to understand this subject matter, the analysis established the extent to which existing research has progressed towards clarifying the problem inconsistencies, gaps, contradictions, and identifying relations in the literature; three was formulation of a general overarching conceptualization that guided the analysis, commented on, evaluated, and developed a general conceptual analytical framework upon which the understanding of the cause of environmental damage, and its apposite solution and implications for practice and policy proposed in this paper were anchored on. The review started by identifying the specific research question this study wanted to figure out, that is, whether the current approaches of understanding environmental damages, proposed causes and recommended solutions are explained in light of the prevailing capital social relations. Do such efforts acknowledge the processes, mechanisms, and structures upon which the discernible

attributes are built? This was followed by a thorough clarification of whether the planned systematic review had already been done and the extent.

Since the analysis aimed at conducting a search that was exhaustive, and therefore, representative of most of the studies which have focused on the topic of interest, the identification of the search terms which were carefully broken down from the main research question so as to help find as many potentially relevant articles as possible to include was done. Techniques such as the use of synonyms, singular/plural forms, verbal forms, adjectives, different spellings, broader/narrower terms, and taxonomical terms used by databases to organize their contents into categories listed by headings and sub-headings were also employed to increase the search horizon. Having reached this stage, the aim was to find all available published and unpublished work which addressed the research question, operationalised through the search terms. The best way to find the vast majority of published work which addressed the research question was to comprehensively utilise at least two different renowned electronic "Environmental Databases", the NETRONLINE and UNEP Environmental Data Explorer. The search also extended to other credible and academic search engines such as Google Scholar, Educational Resources Information Centre, Google Book Search, GetCITED, DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals), BioOne, Opengray, Opendoar, ScienceDirect, and WorldCat databases for dissertations and theses for the purpose of maximising the scope for more information.

As a result, numerous information was obtained, but further reduced significantly by the aid of formulating the inclusion and exclusion criteria which primarily focused only on the most relevant literature on the research question, conceptualization and key variables. In order to arrive at this point, the titles and/or abstracts of all work identified by the searches were read. Those which qualified for inclusion, the full-text versions, were therefore sifted to extract the most relevant information. Without understating the significance of field information, systematic review enabled to exhaustively review both published and unpublished, and ongoing studies, and thus, presenting a more accurate, reliable, than individual studies.

3.0: Capitalism

Capitalism has been at the centre of social, political, cultural and economic debates particularly in the developing world (Floyd, 2006; Maurice, 2012; Dobb, 1996; Douglas, 1997). While the supporters claim that the system gives an opportunity to progress with free market driven economy, and the liberty to produce and consume what one wants to rather than what the government decides for someone, something considered to be a violation of the UN Human Rights Declaration, opponents on the other hand maintain that the same has inflicted fatal consequences to millions of poor people all around the world (Paul and Stuart, 2009; William, 1987; Maurice, 2012; Edwards, et al., 2006; Ross and Trachte, 2000). One are that has suffered from capitalism is the environment.

Synthesized from various writings, capitalism is an economic system hinged on the private ownership of production inputs and capital, and on the provision services and production of goods for profit. This production is guided by the principle of supply and demand in the general market, rather than through central planning. Capitalism is commonly characterised by competition between producers. Other aspects, such as the participation of the government in setting out the rules of the game and in production differ across variant types of capitalism. The system rose to prominence with the end of feudal economies, and has now turned to be one most dominant economic system all around the world (Maurice, 2012; Floyd, 2006; James, 2009; Michael, 2014; David, 2013; Stockman, 2013). Specific tenets of capitalism, such as property rights and wage labour, can also be considered cornerstones of representative government. It is often closely linked to economic growth, whereas price and production targets and volumes are set by the market instead of governments. And with the assistance of private property rights individuals have the freedom to provide services and produce goods according to the market demands.

One important characteristic that makes it powerful is the fact that it dominates nearly all corners of the world (Floyd, 2006; Paul and Stuart, 2009; Douglas, 1997), and operates in a way that it is indiscernible to many. In the words of Cypher (2009);

... we are, in actual fact, to a great extent unaware of this now a worldly framework, much as fish are heedless of the water in which

they swim. It is capitalism's moral code, standpoint, frame of mind, and final intent that we integrate and acculturate to as we grow up. Unwittingly, we come to admit that covetousness, exploitative behaviours, and competitive trait among the countries, corporations, businesses, and ourselves are not only the norms and moral codes of our way of life but are in fact appropriate for society since they make our economy work efficiently...

The quote above only admits that capitalism is such a unique system, among other social and economic systems, in its active and extreme cultivation of individual self-interest. The attitudes and mores needed for the smooth functioning and maintenance of such a system, as well as for people to thrive as members of society such as greed, individualism, competitiveness, exploitation of others, and consumerism are inculcated into people by both the primary and secondary agents of socialisation such as families and schools; and the media and the workplace respectively (Blumer, 1969; Major, et al., 2005; Berger and Luckman, 1966).

It is primarily because of these inherent tenets, the system has been criticised for its principal focus on profit, and how that focus has led to social and economic inequality and marginalization, particularly in the developing countries; it has actually not worked for the many poor. Further, it is also criticised for its emphasis on consumption, as the constant purchase of goods and services, which is essentially necessary for capitalism's success.

4.0: Capitalism and Environmental Damage

The big question that environmentalists usually do not ask is why all of this tragedy on the environment all over the world is happening?. They are, generally, worried with some other issues and sometimes they are even loosely connected with ecological problems such as global warming, chemical pollution, soil degradation, deforestation, acidification etc. But why are they all occurring? Without digging into how the current capital social relation actually functions in the real world (not theoretically), it is not possible to answer the question. Various accounts have been offered on the same, but only a handful have essentially been able to render the real critique on the capitalist economic system itself and there is no consideration given to alternative ways to organise and run an economy. Similarly, Curtis (2009) indicates the same concern. He claims that environmentalists

are not very good at asking, let alone answering fundamental questions when it comes to environmental damages. For example, a fundamental question such as why the damaging of the environment is happening almost in all parts of the world? It will be difficult to come up with genuine and enduring solutions if we are unable to satisfactorily answer this seemingly unchallenging question to environmentalists.

The argument for this paper is that most of the critical environmental problems we have today are either brought about, or aggravated much, by the workings of the capitalist economic system. Indeed, even such issues as technology and population growth are best explained and make sense of their contribution in terms of their relation to the socioeconomic structure of the social organisation. Ecological issues are not merely the resultant of human inexperience and lack of knowledge or inherent ravenousness. They do not surface because the owners of large enterprises are in short supply of production ethics and morals. Rather, we should focus on the underlying workings of the social, political, and economic systems for adequate explanations. It is exactly from the logic and nature of the capitalist system that the ecological problems are built into.

Under the capitalistic economic system, while the majority have a considerable interest in preserving and sustaining a healthy ecological system, the minority which is the capitalist ruling class is not responsible for the former, except when the ruling class seeks to bring on board the demands of the majority in order to maintain the system. Although the global resources are controlled by a few economically and politically powerful people, planning is not centralised under capitalism (Douglas, 1997; Edward, et al., 2006; Michael, 2014). Instead, production is anarchic; it is centered on making profits, not around meeting essential human needs. A large amount of what is produced under the capitalist framework is uncalled for and wasteful, and the system is reluctant and incapable of incorporating long-term human survival as a need (Joseph, 1998/1892; Alexander, 2007). Further, within the capitalist system resources are not equitably distributed. A significant section of the population does not have adequate resources for survival, a situation that inevitably leads to environmental problems. In an interview with the International Union for Conservation of Nature in 2014, Lester Brown, the founder of Worldwatch Institute attested that;

... the food crisis in the South is an outcome of either inadequate or lack of access to, and poor distribution of the resources that are available. Most of the arable and highly productive land is occupied by a few elites, bureaucrats, and business people who do not necessarily commit the resource to the betterment of the many poor and who need it the most. This forces the growing poor population to compete for a scarce resource for survival, a state that mostly culminates into environment damages that we are all witnessing in the region. But even when used for production, the environmental 'costs of production' are neither factored in the production equation nor accounted for in the market, and can thus, be written off by businesses as adverse externalities, or free gifts, and environmental degradation is ultimately unaccounted for...

Furthermore, capitalism is not static. It has changed since it first arose out of the demise of the feudal aristocracies of medieval Europe 200 years ago. Today, it has metamorphosed and developed to its highest stage: imperialism (James, 2009; Douglas, 1997; Michael, 2014). Under imperialism, the capitalists carve and re-carve the social formation. The unevenly distribution of resources acquire a distinctly national flavor, with a division of the world into developed countries, on the one hand, and developing and neo-colonies, on the other. Capitalism exploits both the human and natural resources of developing nations. In their attempts to reshape, and control the world, the capitalists invest significantly in lethal and highly destructive weapons of mass destruction. The process of producing, testing, analysing, and use of these chemical and biological weapons is another, but highly sophisticated dais in which the system wreaks havoc on the environment. In accordance with the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) Annual Report of 2014:

... the use and air testing of weapons be it biological, chemical or even without such ingredients discharge large amounts of poisonous soot powder into the air. When soot reflects sunlight, cause a cooling effect on the climate at a global scale. This has possibly been concealing a portion of the impact of Carbon dioxide induced global warming. In this event, the ozone layer gets damaged, the temperatures drop, and the production of essential staple crops supporting millions of people all over the world gets seriously hampered ...

The system does not only have a commanding influence on the military, economic, and political spheres, it also dominates the social and cultural institutions which work tirelessly to propagate and

reinforce its ideology and moral codes (IDCCCPP, 2014). Capitalism promotes and celebrates individualism, an ideology that values individuals and small groups' interests at the expense of the larger, let alone human beings. Such interests are all the time geared towards profit maximization and at the shortest time possible, given the unforeseen socioeconomic predicaments (Edward, 2010; Edwards, et al., 2006). This ideology, too, is harmful to the environment. For instance, business owners and managers generally give high priority to short-term gains in their operations. A large number takes into account the coming three to five years, or, in some rare instances, up to ten years (Michael, 2014; Stephen, 2011). This is the way they must function because of unforeseeable business environments and conditions (for instance, prices of the required inputs, costs of production, tax regimes, competition, etc) and pressure from speculators who strive for short-term returns. Hence, they act in ways that are to a great extent unmindful of the ecological limits to the end gains and as though in their world there will never be a limited supply of natural resources for their economic undertaking. Evidences from countries that have so far experienced critical depletion of their natural resource such as the Democratic Republic of Congo and India reveal that when facts on natural resource reserves were known to capitalists in the name of investors, it only accelerated the extraction of the nearly exhausted resources other than slowing it down so that they could move on to new areas of resource exploitation. When every single capitalist is consumed up with the goal of making and maximizing profit, collectively this has devastating consequences on the environment and human survival at large. Faced with limited natural resources, there is no rational way to prioritise under a modern capitalist system.

The well-documented decline of many aquatic species, almost to the point of extinction, is an example of how profit maximisation and individuals' interests override communal's and rationality. For example, it is always in the short-term individual's interests of the larger scale fishers, some of whom use bottom trawlers and operate at factory stage, to catch, process, and freeze fishery resources to gain, but more importantly, maximize their profit. Hence, the fishery resources face unprecedented depletion in the process, and in the end, extinct. No one protects the "common interest" (Daniel, 2009; Thomas, 2012; Marx, 1970; Marx, 1906). In a system run generally on private self-interest with the purpose of accumulating assets and

capital, the state is normally incapable of doing so. The phenomenon is sometimes referred to as the 'tragedy of the commons'¹.

Moreover, capitalism ideology by and large associates development with economic growth (Juan, 2004; Joan, 1983; David, 2013). This perspective of development considers rise in the per capita income, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), increase in the level of investment, industrialization, technology and markets, amongst other quantitative aspects as indicators of development. A developed economy is considered to be one that carries on production with a large amount of capital investment, a large amount of machinery and using advanced techniques (Ibid; Benjamin, 2007; Lewellen, 1995). The available human and other resources are employed to the maximum, and consequently, the production efficiency is very high leading to high per capita incomes. More often, this kind of development makes less and sometimes no difference between destructive and productive activities depending on the nature of political regimes in place. Whereas a genuine index of development would separate costs and benefits, this kind of development assign a positive significance on all dealings and transactions and then adds it to the total value. The GDP has no way of assessing the value of natural assets until they enter the financial economy, or simply put, consumed (Lewellen, 1995). For example, a tree in an old-forest which offers us and various other creatures numerous amenities such as rain, food, medicine, shade, wind-breaker, water, shelter, etc worth less or nothing to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) up until it is cut down to produce timber which will be sold and assigned value. Thereafter, the GDP is not held accountable for the loss of a range of services curtailed by its reckless desired for growth and expansion. Therefore, by aiming at consumption other than human social, economic, and cultural development, the GDP directly participates in the depletion of finite natural resources. The extent to which capitalism is capable of instigating environmental destruction, if not dismantled, is well captured in the testimony provided by the Tanzanian WWF country

¹ The tragedy of the commons is an economic theory of a state of affairs within a shared resource framework where an individual user(s) act rationally and independently for their own self-interest and in a manner that is contrary to the common good of all users by depleting that resource. For further explanation, refer to Hardin, G (1968); 'The Tragedy of the Commons', in *Science* 162 (3859): 1243–1248.

representative when addressing the crowd during The World Environmental Day in 2014:

....almost everywhere we visited in Africa, foreign commercial companies were exploiting natural resources after signing contracts with the governments. Prodigious logs, four to five feet in width were brought out of the virgin forests, natural gas and oil were being shipped from the coastal region, minerals from mining sites, and offshore fishing privileges had been sold to foreign corporations, and exploration of minerals and oil was ongoing in the interior. And because of the hugely expanded scale of today's economy under the pretext economic growth, myriad sophisticated technologies were widely engaged in the exploitation of the natural resources in poor developing countries. In a few years, the resources of the continent and others alike will be annihilated...

From the quote above, suffice it to expand our conceptualization of the system that capitalism is not just an economic system, but a scheme that fashions the political, legal and social organizations to support the system of wealth and accumulation which essentially include also exploiting natural resources. The conniving and dubious relationships that exist today between law, politics and business interests are so apparent to most analysts and observers (Bradley, 2009; Holcombe, 2002; McChesney, 2007; Mills, 1956; Stockman, 2013; Truman, 2001). These range from tangibles, such as bribery, to the more subdued forms, such as buying friendships, lobbying, buying access, supporting and sponsoring social events, and pledging for political support, etc. Because of the immediate perceptible gains political leaders amass out of such arrangements, increasingly they begin to perceive themselves as part, and therefore, become advocates of the system. It is from this deceptive relationship, political leaders turn slowly into political entrepreneurs and hegemonic representatives other capitalist. Their ideological capture is always justified by their re-election into office which is supposedly in the best interest of the public. In the corridors of justice, there are deliberate efforts from individuals and political leaders to protect the interests and businesses of the capitalists.

... as corporations expand, or begin to saturate, they will always search for new markets elsewhere to sell their goods and services. These corporations with the help of their governments that work tirelessly on behalf of corporate and countries' interests to secure entry, access and control over vital natural resources like a variety of

minerals, and most importantly. Developing countries are in the middle of a land-grab phenomenon, as private capital and powerful governments commit billions to gain control of millions of acres throughout the world but mostly in developing countries to set up machineries and plants, to produce biofuel feedstock crops and to food and for their home and world markets. Today, it is estimated that more than thirty million hectares of land, roughly close to two-thirds of all the arable land in Europe, the larger portion being in Africa, have been acquired by rich countries and larger corporations. Today multinational corporations scratch the world to find investing opportunities and resources anywhere they can find, exploiting cheap labour in these countries, and thus, creating more divide other than reducing it. The outcome is a more voracious exploitation of nature ... [Stockman, 2013]

A critical transformative position, which this paper is putting forward in comprehending the system and addressing the environmental question, would have been cruel and uncalled for if communities (the majority poor and average people) that virtually depend on the environment for their survival and their governments managed or have the control over the environment instead of business corporations. These corporations are subject to the single-minded goal of maximizing short-term profits and thereafter advancing to other sites in the name of development, leaving damages behind curtailing the sustenance human kind and the ecosystem in general. Given the influence exercised by capitalists over the state, media, economy, military, politics, and social institutions, it is pointless to introduce changes that will never come to life. It is almost impossible to propose and effect fundamental changes that they oppose. As such, viable, rational, and ecologically sound policies will be difficult to realize.

5.0: Unconvincing Solutions

Presently, there is no shortage of ideas about what to do as far as environmental problems are concerned. Several solutions, both globally and locally, have been offered in response to the same, particularly, in the third world countries. Most of these solutions, however, are fallacious and by and large are engineered by those who represent the capital social relations, which in the opinion of this paper, are responsible for many environmental problems occurring today. These solutions include purchasing green products,

purchasing carbon credits to offset the global warming effects, afforestation, blasting the atmosphere with particles to reflect sunlight, limiting population, developing systems for taking carbon dioxide out of the atmosphere and storing it deep underground, and imposing a tax on all fossil fuels (a carbon tax) amongst others (Hajer, 2005; World Resource Institute, 2012; UNEP, 2011, Ecology Global Network, 2011; Environmental Protection Agency, 2012; UNEP, 2015). Some of these make more sense than the other. Others present unclear consequences. Nonetheless, they all give the impression that it is really possible to address the current worldly ecological predicament without grappling with capitalism, as the structural and institutional arrangements that inform and guide the day to day social, political, and economic operations of society. Quite the contrary, it is capitalism's craving for incessant growth and its sole overriding objective of getting more profits that are at the apex of the environmental crisis the world is facing today.

Some of the worldliest dominant and leading institutions that either explicitly or implicitly in their endeavors fight against environmental problems include the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF); International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI); United Nations Environmental Management Group (UNEMG); and United Nations Populations Fund (UNFPA) amongst others. Such institutions have taken an approach based on the notion that Third World "overpopulation," and not First World overconsumption, is responsible for resource depletion. For them, population growth sits at the apex of all environmental problems in the developing countries (WWF, 2011; UNEMG, 2011; UNFPA, 2010; IFPRI, 2010 and OECD, 2011). Their prescription sounds innocent on the surface, because they call it "sustainable development". Nevertheless, behind this sincere-sounding rhetoric lies the imperialist conniving agenda.

In light of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), "if necessities are to be met on a reasonable and sustainable manner, the world's natural assets must be protected, conserved, and enhanced" (UN-Brundtland Report, 1987). This statement is not as innocent as it appears, for it obscures the fundamental concern of the growing population in the poor developing countries. Capitalist nations are worried that the ever-growing population may shorten their exploitative and reckless use of the Third World natural resources, and thus, the emphasis on sustainable development. Furthermore, the dogma is silent on the prevailing unsustainable

resource use by the world's powers and unfeasible sociopolitical structures that aid the destruction. To be exact, the general concept of 'sustainable development' is advanced to guarantee a continual supply of raw materials and an expanding market for Multinational Corporations (MNCs) on a continuous basis, thereby expanding the neo-colonial global order as it is (James, 2010).

In addition to the proposed zero population growth by many environmental economists, political economists, and demographers, including Thomas Robert Malthus (1766-1834), whose contribution on population studies through his book, *An Essay on the Principle of Population*, is highly treasured, many such as Xepapadeas and Zeeuw (2009), Tzouvelekas, et al., (2007), Panayotou (2000), Jorgenson and Wilcoxon (2000), and Grossman and Krueger (2005), amongst others, advocate a "freezing" of the economy to sustain current levels of prosperity. This proposition, however, is considered oxymoron and antithetical to the basic laws of capitalism, since the very heart of the system is production of goods and services for the purposes of making profits, which propels growth (David, 2013; Benjamin, 2007; Juan, 2004). This is possible when companies and stock become more valuable, by making more profit than they had before. But in the absence gains in economic activities, it will be impossible to generate increase in consumption, and therefore no available markets to expand into. And therefore, it becomes difficult for the economy to expand, and thus, profits fall flat. The impetus to invest disappears. With the need for development, which in the capitalist world entails economic growth, there is the need for excessive resources, the need for sophisticated technology, expanding into new markets, and thus, more environmental destruction. This closes the window of capitalism system being anything other-than a framework that propels environmental destruction. This is not to completely dismiss the fact that, indeed, it is likely to have such mechanisms as "better environmental regulations" and usage of controlled and fewer toxic chemicals. But the need to grow more, produce more and sell more while not recognizing limits and with profit maximization being the main impetus for production and service provision, indisputably, the system will forever be environmentally damaging. Reasonable or zero-growth is an economic tragedy in a capitalist community.

Like the concept of 'sustainable development', which is well articulated in the Brundtland Report², the "Green Revolution"³ has in practice been an ideological smokescreen for Western dominance over the neo-colonies. While the green revolution succeeded in increasing food production in the Third World, it failed to increase food consumption in the Third World on the other hand, as the surplus was curved for export to capitalist countries. Furthermore, the revolution has greatly reduced the varieties of crops to be planted. As such, this has created a perfect breeding ground for future famine. The revolution also relies heavily on chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Lappe and Collins, 2008) and therefore highly toxic.

Another mistaken approach to solving the problems of environmentalism is the retrograde Neo-Luddite approach which was favored and strongly used by Mohandas Gandhi (1869-1948), Murray Bookchin (1921-2006), Theodore John (1942), and many other utopian types in their struggle against environmental destruction. Many neo-colonized nations such as Philippines people, however, do not wish to do away with self-reliant industrialism development, as Moorhead (2013) declares:

... the worst propaganda of the pro-imperialist environmentalists idealize industrial underdevelopment as the healthy preservation of the natural environment and obscure the unhealthy conditions and consequences of underdevelopment and poverty as well as the vulnerability of the underdeveloped and poor countries to imperialist plunder and pollution ...

² *Our Common Future*, also known as *the Brundtland Report*, prepared by WCED and was published in 1987. Its purpose was to bring together all nations and in collaborations in the search for a more responsible path for development commonly known as 'sustainable development'. The report wanted to reconnect, echo and bring to light the feelings and spirit of the United Nations Conference on the "Human Environment" held in Stockholm, within which the call was made for nations to include environmental issues in the political domain. The report therefore glued the environmental matters firmly on the political agenda. As such, the report suggests that environment and development should, henceforth be discussed as one single issue

³ This is the period during the mid and late 20th century when productivity and efficiency in agriculture occurred as a result of significant improvement in science and technology. During this period, improved seeds, effective pesticides and herbicides, and chemical fertilizers were created. All these technological innovations and development led to increased productivity, and hence, yields.

Disapproving industrialism entirely in essence is subscribing to Neo-Luddite movement. For those who endorse such a position will need to shed light on how the absence of industrialized economies will put a stop on capitalists' interest to expand for profit or defeat capitalists in wars and also be able to avail the seriously needed reform in the health care and other basic socioeconomic services. If capitalists can march right in and take over non-capitalist communities, these people will have flopped in their freedom battles. But again, if there is lack of medical supplies, water, electricity or various other basic needs for survival, then the triumph of freedom will be tantamount to bankrupt. Unlike the capital social relation, the communal social relation will not abrogate national sovereignty for purposes of industrial development (Oscar, 2008; David, 2011). But they will struggle for the correct line to prevail if that issue arises. And contrary to the essentialised notions of some idealists, we believe most indigenous people will embrace industrial movement and advancement that serves as opposed to undermines the general population's needs and interests.

The other unfitting approach to environmental problems is what this paper would refer to as the liberal reformism strategy. This comes in many superficial forms. There is the direct approach of Ralph Nader's Public Interest Research Group (PIRG), which proposes that environmentalists and environment-loving individuals ought to lobby the bureaucrats and lawmakers for reforms. There is the activist reformist approach of Greenpeace and the Sea Shepard Society, which suggests that civil disobedience will help to pressure the capitalist legislators for reforms. Then comes the "consciousness-raising" approach put forward by eco-feminists and the New Age "deep ecology" approaches others. This common reformist approach recommends that people should spread ecological knowledge to other people who are not aware of the same (Mathews, 2009). This approach, however, has the problem of presuming that the temperaments of average/poor people are aware about what is more problematic and not the deeds of multinational organisations and capitalists. Therefore, in addition to well-wishers liberals, multinational corporations are fond of the idea that everybody is liable for the current ecological problems in the world. One famous manifestation of this ideology is the government and corporate sponsored "Environmental and Cleanliness Day" events mostly in developing countries, which, by and large, advance the individualistic reformist theme. This approach fails to acknowledge

that it is the materialistic interests, which motivate capitalists to carve up the planet and its resources, and instead, blames the supposedly average people for their ignorance on environmental knowledge.

In the same vain, a score of environmentalists who have attempted to offer the solutions for environmental damages feel that it is probable to solve most of our environmental problems by simply tampering with the capitalist economic system, calling for better regulations, trying to factor in the costs of damage done to the environment into prices of products, introducing greater energy efficiency, replacing fossil fuels for green energy, inventing technologies to amend the problems (World Resources Institute, 2012; Ecology Global Network, 2011; Environmental Protection Agency, 2012) while keeping the essence of capitalism intact. Nevertheless, in the opinion of this paper it is clear that mere technical fixes in the prevailing productive framework will not be sufficient to completely solve the current and potentially ecological catastrophes the world faces. Indeed, the problem with the current approaches is that they permit the economy to continue trending on the same tragic path it is currently on.

In addition, the paper argues that solutions proposed for environmental problems, which would permit the current arrangements of distribution and production to continue unabated, are not genuine solutions. Such arrangements will exacerbate the situation since they offer an incorrect impression that environmental problems are en route to being dealt with when the fact of the matter is very opposite. The complex ecological issues confronting the world and its inhabitants will not be viably managed until we install in another life supporting system that will inform the way we make decisions, how much to produce, what to produce, how to communicate with nature and so on. Our essential and most sound objectives require that we consider satisfying fundamental human needs, and creating just and reasonable conditions on behalf of present and future generations.

6.0 Conclusion

The foregoing analysis points to the fact that the current ecological tragedy almost all over the world cannot be resolved by the same logic that created it. This is fundamentally because the system is clearly unsustainable in its quest for incessant accumulation of capital which leads to the kind of production that continually expand to

provide profits, but at the same time causing environmental destruction on a wider scale; its food and industrial production processes and mechanisms pollute the ecosystem; despite using the highly sophisticated and mechanized technology in the production of goods and provision of services, still it fails to guarantee universal access to a sufficient quantity and quality of food and services; its rampancy nature as far as the destruction of the environment is concerned; its continual creation of unprecedented gap between the rich and the poor within and between countries; and its insincere search for technological miracles to avert growing ecological problems created from and by its processes among others.

The paper strongly agrees with a few other environmentalists who have concluded that continuing with the current system is an apposite path to global environmental disaster. In order to put a stop on the ecological footmarks of human beings on the environment, it is essential that we revert to an economy essentially in the highly industrialized countries which does not encourage unreasonable growth, in order to be able to end, reduce, or if possible reverse the negative effects already registered on the ground. Some environmentalists, such as Wangari (2010), Brower (1995), and Lovelock (2014), are concerned that, if the world output keeps on swelling and the majority of people in developing countries strive to either copy the development philosophy or achieve the standard of living of the developed capitalist nations, not only will pollution continue but also increase beyond what the earth system can endure.

As such, the transition to a sound ecology, which must be a communal social relations economy, is inexorable. This transition will not be simple, rather a steep ascent and will not occur overnight; it is a dynamic, multifaceted struggle for a new cultural compact and a new productive system. It must begin, however, by opposing the logic of capital, endeavoring to produce in the interstices of the system a new communal and social metabolism deep-rooted in community and egalitarianism. The roots and rationale for the creation of the new form of development (sustainable human development) must be born out of the capitalism system, but without being part of it, in as much as the capitalistic form of development itself ascended in the pores of feudal system (Joseph, 1997/1963; David, 2008). Eventually, these initiatives will become stronger enough to create the foundation for the environmental friendly social relation.

Under the proposed framework, questions like how can we supply everyone with essential human needs such as water, health care, education, clothing, and food, how much of produce should be produced, how much and what should be invested, how much should be consumed, and how should the investments be directed are necessary. In the course, people ought to discover appropriate means to conduct the activities in the manner that would not compromise the nature. As such, new forms of institutions will be needed; with a special focus on human life which would inevitably include the ecology which supports human life. For this to ensue, it will require both philosophical and institutional re-arrangement, both at the micro and macro levels, in the interest of and by, and not just ostensibly for, the people (Walter and Cottrell, 2003; *The Economist*, 2010; Herman, 1990; Fred, 2008; David, 2008).

An economic system that is democratic, able to set limits on production and consumption and more importantly reasonably egalitarian must satisfy the basic material and non-material needs of the entire population, while protecting the environment. Contrary to what the capitalistic ideology communicates to us, the environment is never a phenomenon which exists out of human economy; rather, it constitutes the very fundamental life support systems for all living creatures. To heal what Karl Marx referred to as “metabolic rift⁴” between the environment and economy, entails new ways of manufacturing, producing, living, transportation and so forth (Marx, 1981; Bellamy, 2000). Such a society must be sustainable; and sustainability requires substantive and functional balance, built in an egalitarian mode of production and consumption (Ibid; Oscar, 2008; Paul, 1999; Lange, 2010; Luis, 1988; David, 2011). We must strive to develop a credible framework; one in which bureaucracy is held in line, and control over politics and production really lives with the people. In the same way as new challenges that go up against us are

⁴ This is Karl Marx's impression of the "irrevocable crevice in the interdependent process of social metabolism. He hypothesized a break in interaction between humankind and nature stemming from the capital social relations. In Marx's conception, this seems to present the highest nature of alienation where the natural co-existence of nature and humankind is shut down. This also demonstrates the complex and dynamic interchange between human beings and nature, resulting from the capitalist mode of production

changing in our time, so are the conceivable outcomes for the development of freedom and sustainability.

In sum, capitalism is the root cause of most environmental problems in both developed and developing countries. Environmental solutions, therefore, which barely leave the system intact, cannot be expected to resolve the problem, but reinforce it. Therefore, a genuine and naturally caring system is required all through to relieve the world from the root causes of degradation, pollution and overconsumption.

References

- Alexander, C., 2007. *The Rape of the Fair Country*, New York: Bantam.
- Bean T., 2009. Organizational Socialization: An Integrative Review. *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, 4, 101-145.
- Bellamy, J., 2000. *Marx's Ecology: Materialism and Nature*, New York: Monthly Review Press, p. ix
- Berger, P.L., Luckman, T., 1966. *The Social Construction of Reality*. New York: Doubleday.
- Benjamin, F., 2007. Capitalism, economic growth & democracy. *Daedalus* 136(3): 46-55
- Blumer, H., 1969. *Symbolic Interactionism: Perspectives and Method*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Bradley, R. L. Jr., 2009. *Capitalism at Work: Business and Governments*. Salem, Mass.: M&M Scrivener Press.
- Brower, D. and Steve, C., 1994. *Let the Mountains Talk, Let the Rivers Run* (New York: HarperCollins, 1995). ISBN 0-06-251430-X
- Curtis. W., 2009. *Barbaric Heart: Capitalism and the Crisis of Nature*, Orion (May-June 2009), <http://orionmagazine.org/index.php/articles/article/4680>.
- Daniel, B., 2009. *The Cultural Contradictions of Capitalism*. New York: Basic Books.
- David, B., 2013. The false promise of Capitalism, *Scientific American*, August 2011, pp. 59-65.
- David, M., 2011. *Market, State and Community: Theoretical Foundations of Market Socialism*, Oxford: Clarendon Press
- Dobb, M., 1996. *Studies in the Development of Capitalism*. London: Routledge.
<https://mises.org/sites/default/files/Theory%20of%20Socialis>

m%20and%20Capitalism,%20A_4.pdf

Douglas, D., 1997. *The Twisted Dream: Capitalist Development in the United States Since 1776*. Boston: Winthrop Publishers.

Ecology Global Network. 2011. Ecology Global Network. Retrieved August 10, 2011, from Ecology Global Network: <http://ecology.com/features/paperchase/>

Edward N., 2010. *Growth, Accumulation and Unproductive Activity*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Edwards, R. C., Reich, M., and Weisskopf, T. E. (eds.), 2006. (third edition). *The Capitalist System: A Book of Readings*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.

Ehrlich, P., & Holdren, J., 1991. The impact of population growth. *Science*, 171, 1212–1217

Environmental Protection Agency. 2012. Environmental Protection Strategy. Retrieved September 24, 2012, from [epa.gov](http://www.epa.gov/tri/stakeholders/datausers/index.htm) <http://www.epa.gov/tri/stakeholders/datausers/index.htm>

Floyd, C., 2006. *Understanding Capital: Marx's Economic Theory*. Harvard University Press.

Grossman G. M. and Krueger, A. B., 2005. Economic Growth and the Environment, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, MIT Press, vol. 110(2), pages 353-77, May.

Hajer, M., 2005. *The politics of environmental discourse: Ecological modernization and the policy process*, Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press

Holcombe, R.G., 2002. Political Entrepreneurship and the Democratic Allocation of Economic Resources. *Review of Austrian Economics* 15 (2–3): 143–59

IFPRI. 2010. *Food Security, Farming, and Climate Change to 2050: Scenarios, Results, Policy Options*, Washington, DC.

International Department, Central Committee, Communist Party of the

- Philippines (IDCCPP). 2014. On the Issue of the Environment in the World and in the Philippines, 31 March 2014, p. 1.
- James, P. J., 2010. Non-Governmental Voluntary Organisations: The True Mission, Mass Line Publications, TKMC (P.O.), Kollam 691005, Kerala, India
- James, C., 2009. Crisis Tendencies of the 1990s: Constraints on the Ideology of Globalization. Unpublished
- Joan, R., 1983. The Economics of Imperfect Competition. London: Macmillan.
- Jorgenson D. W. and Wilcoxon, P. J., 2000. Environmental Regulation and U.S. Economic Growth, The RAND Journal of Economics, 21-2, 314-340.
- Joseph, C. (1998/1892). The Heart of Darkness. New York: Signet Classics.
- Juan, K., 2004. The Theory of Economic Development: An Inquiry into Profit, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle: Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- Jowett, Benjamin, 1871. The dialogues of Plato. Vol. III. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lappe, F.M., Collins J., Rosset, P. and Esparza, L., 2008. World Hunger: Twelve Myths, 2nd edition, Grove Press, New York.
- Lange, O., 2010. On the Economic Theory of Socialism, Minneapolis, Minn.: University of Minnesota Press
- Lewellen, T. C., 1995. Dependency and Development: An Introduction to the Third World (Westport, Conn.: Bergin & Garvey, 1995)
- Lovelock, J., 2014. A Rough Ride to the Future. Allen Lane. ISBN 978-0241004760.
- Luis, L., 1988. The Computer and the Market', in Charles Feinstein (ed.) Socialism, Capitalism and Economic Growth: Essays

Presented to Maurice Dobb, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press

- Major, D. A., Kozlowski, S. W. J., Chao, F. T., and Gardner, P.D., 2005. A longitudinal investigation of newcomer expectations, early socialization outcomes, and the moderating effect of role development factors. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80, 418-431.
- Marx, K. and Engels ([1845]1977). *The Germany Ideology*, Lawrence and Wishart, London
- Marx, K., 1981. *Capital*, vol. III. New York: Vintage, p. 949
- Marx, K., 1970. *A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy*. Moscow: Progress Publishers.
- Marx, K., 1906. *Capital: A Critique of Political Economy*. Vol. I. New York: Modern Library.
- Mathews, M.R., 2009. Social and Environmental Accounting: A Practical Demonstration of Ethical Concern? *Journal of Business Ethics* 14: 663-671
- Maurice, D., 2012. *Political Economy and Capitalism*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- McChesney F.S., 2007. *Money for Nothing: Politicians, Rent Extraction, and Political Extortion*. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- Michael, T., 2014. *World Struggle for Power and Wealth*. New York: Monthly Review Press.
- Mills, C. W., 1956. *The Power Elite*. New York: Oxford University Press
- Moorhead, A., 2013. *Climate, agriculture and food security: A strategy for change*, CGIAR.
- Morrison, K., 1983. *Formation of Modern Social Thought*, Thousand Oaks: SAGE London
<http://oll.libertyfund.org/titles/plato-dialogues-vol-3-republic->

timaeus-critias

- OECD, 2011. *Towards Green Growth*, Paris.
- Oscar L., 2008. *On the Economic Theory of Socialism*. University of Minnesota Press,
- Panayotou T., 2000. *Economic Growth and the Environment*. CID Working Papers 56, Center for International Development at Harvard University.
- Paul, G., 1999. *Socialist and Non-socialist Industrialisation Patterns: A Comparative Appraisal*, New York: Praeger,
- Paul, B. and Stuart, W., 2009. *Monopoly Capital: An Essay on the American Economic and Social Order*. New York: Monthly Review Press.
- Ross, S. and Trachte, C., 2000. *Global Capitalism*. Albany: State University of New York Press
- Stephen, L., 2011. *Capitalism and Catastrophe: A Critical Appraisal of the Limits to Capitalism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Stockman, D.A., 2013. *The Great Deformation: The Corruption of Capitalism*. New York: Public Affairs Press
- Thomas, M., 2012. *Capitalism and Individualism: Reframing the Argument for the Free Society*. New York: St. Martin's Press
- Truman, D.B., 2001. *The Plight of Capitalism: The Political and Governmental Process in Africa*, New York: Doubleday.
- Tzouvelekas V., Vouvaki D. and Xepapadeas, A. (2007), *Total Factor Productivity Growth and the Environment: A Case for Green Growth Accounting*. FEEM Working Paper Series, 42
- United Nations Environment Programme Annual Report 2014. <http://web.unep.org/ourplanet/may-2015/unep-publications/united-nations-environment-programme-annual-report-2014>
- UNEMG, 2011. *Working towards a Balanced and Inclusive Green Economy: A United Nations System-wide Perspective*, Geneva.

UNEP, 2011. *Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication*, Nairobi.

UNEP, 2015. *Annual Report*, Nairobi, Kenya, <http://UNEP 2015 Annual Report>

UNFPA, 2010. *Impacts of Population Dynamics, Reproductive Health and Gender on Poverty*, UNFPA Concept Paper prepared for the United Nations Summit on the Millennium Development Goals (New York, NY, September 2010), New York, NY

UN-WCED, 1987. *Our Common Future/Brundtland Report*, Washington

Wangari, M.M., 2010. *Replenishing the Earth: Spiritual Values for Healing Ourselves and the World*; New York: Doubleday

William, A., 1987. *A Short History of the World Economy since 1850*. London: Longman

World Wide Fund for Nature, 2011. *Living Planet Report*. Gland, Switzerland.: WWF International

World Resources Institute [WRI], 2012. *Pilot Analysis of Global Ecosystems (PAGE)*. World Resources Institute, Maryland.

Xepapadeas A. and Zeeuw, A., 2009. *Environmental Policy and Competitiveness: The Porter Hypothesis and the Composition of Capital*, *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 37(2), 165-182. <http://sttpml.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/capitalism-and-its-economics-a-critical-history-douglas-dowd.pdf>